

Robust Liver and Lesion Segmentation on Contrast-Enhanced CT Using Comprehensive Augmentation and Hybrid Dice-Focal Loss

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Abstract. Accurate segmentation of the liver and intrahepatic lesions on contrast-enhanced CT is challenging due to variability in scanners, imaging protocols, and lesion characteristics. We present a robust nnU-Net style framework that addresses these issues using a comprehensive augmentation strategy and a hybrid loss function tailored for rare voxels. The pipeline combines diverse spatial transforms (rotations, scaling, elastic deformations, cropping, mixup, cutout) with intensity transforms (color jitter, brightness/contrast adjustments, Gaussian noise, histogram matching) to improve generalization across acquisition conditions. To handle class imbalance and small-lesion detection, we employ a hybrid Dice and Focal loss, balancing overlap accuracy with sensitivity to difficult cases. Models are trained for 500 epochs with consistent normalization and resampling, achieving stable convergence. In the TriALS 2025 challenge evaluations, our method achieved competitive lesion-wise Dice scores of 0.582 per-case and 0.566 globally, with high precision of 0.850 for cases containing lesions, demonstrating strong liver segmentation and improved performance on challenging lesions.

Keywords: Liver lesion segmentation · Contrast-enhanced CT · nnU-Net · Data augmentation · Hybrid Dice-Focal loss

1 Introduction

Liver cancer remains one of the leading causes of cancer-related mortality worldwide [3,28]. Contrast-enhanced CT plays a pivotal role in diagnosing and monitoring liver diseases [2,14]. Automated segmentation of the liver and hepatic lesions can significantly improve clinical workflows by reducing manual annotation time and enabling quantitative analysis [6,15]. However, achieving robust segmentation remains challenging due to: (1) high variability in imaging protocols, (2) diverse lesion appearances, (3) class imbalance, and (4) unclear boundaries [31,32].

Deep learning approaches, particularly U-Net [24,7] and nnU-Net [13], have demonstrated remarkable success. However, liver lesion segmentation requires

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addressing two critical challenges: generalization across imaging conditions and detection of small lesions. Recent works have explored advanced augmentation [34,8], specialized loss functions [20,16], and multi-scale architectures [35,12,23].

Our contributions: (1) comprehensive augmentation strategy with mixup, cutout, and histogram matching for robustness; (2) hybrid Dice-Focal loss combining volumetric overlap and hard example mining; (3) competitive performance on TriALS 2025 with Dice 0.582 and precision 0.850.

2 Related Work

Liver Segmentation: Early approaches used traditional methods [9,1,11]. Deep learning revolutionized the field with U-Net variants [24,7]. Christ et al. [6] proposed cascaded networks, Li et al. [15] introduced H-DenseUNet, and recent works explored attention [26] and transformers [10,4]. nnU-Net [13] achieved state-of-the-art by automatically configuring architecture and training strategies.

Data Augmentation: Standard techniques include geometric and intensity transforms [27]. Advanced methods like mixup [34], cutout [8], elastic deformations [29], and histogram matching [22] improve generalization [5,33].

Loss Functions: Class imbalance challenges require specialized losses. Dice loss [20] optimizes volumetric overlap, Focal loss [16] handles hard examples, and Tversky loss [25] controls false positives/negatives. Hybrid approaches [18,30] combine multiple losses for better performance.

3 Methodology

3.1 Problem Formulation

Given dataset $\mathcal{X} = \{X_i\}_{i=1}^N$ of contrast-enhanced CT volumes where $X_i \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times D}$, with ground truth $Y_i \in \{0, 1, 2\}^{H \times W \times D}$ (background, liver, lesion), we learn $f_\theta : \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times D} \rightarrow [0, 1]^{H \times W \times D \times C}$ minimizing $\mathcal{L}(f_\theta(X), Y)$.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

We implement standardized preprocessing: (1) **Orientation normalization** to RAS canonical order using SimpleITK; (2) **Intensity normalization** via HU clipping and z-score normalization; (3) **Resampling** to fixed target spacing using spline interpolation (images) and nearest-neighbor (labels); (4) **Patch-based training** with random extraction for memory efficiency and sample diversity.

3.3 Network Architecture

Our model uses nnU-Net architecture [13]: U-shaped encoder-decoder with skip connections. The encoder uses 3D convolutions, instance normalization, and Leaky ReLU, progressively downsampling via strided convolutions. The decoder

Fig. 1. TriALS 2025 Pipeline: Overview of the proposed framework for liver and lesion segmentation. The pipeline consists of triphasic CT volumes (arterial, portal venous, and delayed phases) that undergo comprehensive augmentation (spatial and intensity transforms), processed through an nnU-Net backbone with weighted Dice-Focal loss, optimized using AdamW, and evaluated using multiple metrics (VOE, RMSD, MSD, RVD, ASSD).

mirrors the encoder with transposed convolutions and skip connections for multi-scale feature fusion. We train three variants: (1) **3D Full-Resolution** (patch $128 \times 160 \times 112$, 32 base channels); (2) **3D Low-Resolution** for coarse-to-fine cascade; (3) **2D Variant** (576×448) for ablations.

3.4 Data Augmentation Strategy

Spatial Augmentations: Random rotations ($\pm 15^\circ$), scaling ($0.85\text{--}1.25\times$), elastic deformations [29], random cropping, mixup [34] ($\tilde{X} = \lambda X_i + (1 - \lambda)X_j$ where $\lambda \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha, \alpha)$), and cutout [8] (random rectangular masking).

Intensity Augmentations: Brightness (± 0.2) and contrast ($0.75\text{--}1.25\times$) adjustments, color jitter, Gaussian noise ($\sigma \approx 0.01$), and histogram matching [22] to simulate scanner variations.

3.5 Hybrid Dice-Focal Loss

We combine Dice loss [20] for volumetric overlap:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Dice}} = 1 - \frac{2 \sum_v p_v g_v + \epsilon}{\sum_v p_v + \sum_v g_v + \epsilon} \quad (1)$$

with Focal loss [16] for hard examples:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Focal}} = -\frac{1}{|V|} \sum_{v \in V} \alpha_c (1 - p_{v,c})^\gamma \log(p_{v,c}) \quad (2)$$

where $\gamma = 2$ is the focusing parameter. Our hybrid loss: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{Dice}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{Focal}}$ (equal weights).

3.6 Training and Inference

Training: AdamW optimizer [17] with $lr_0 = 10^{-3}$, polynomial decay ($lr_t = lr_0(1 - t/T)^{0.9}$, $T = 500$), batch size 2 (3D), mixed-precision training [19].

Inference: Sliding-window with Gaussian weighting, optional test-time augmentation, connected-component filtering (remove ≤ 10 voxels), resampling to original space.

4 Experiments and Results

4.1 Dataset and Evaluation

We evaluate on TriALS 2025 challenge dataset with contrast-enhanced CT from multiple institutions. Metrics include lesion-wise Dice (per-case and global), precision/recall (overall and for cases with ≥ 1 lesion), VOE, RVD, and surface distances (ASSD, RMSD, MSD). Implementation in PyTorch on NVIDIA A100 GPUs, training 48-72 hours.

4.2 Challenge Performance

Table 1 shows our results. We achieve lesion Dice 0.582 (per-case) and 0.566 (global), demonstrating reliable segmentation. Overall precision is 0.383 with recall 0.130, indicating conservative detection prioritizing false positive reduction. For cases with lesions, precision increases to 0.850 with recall 0.288, showing accurate segmentation when lesions are detected but missing small/subtle ones.

4.3 Discussion

Strengths: High precision (0.850) for detected lesions shows hybrid loss and augmentation reduce false positives effectively. Competitive Dice scores demonstrate good generalization across multi-center data.

Table 1. Official TriALS 2025 metrics for GenMI.

Metric	Score
Lesion Dice (per-case)	0.582
Lesion Dice (global)	0.566
Lesion Precision	0.383
Lesion Recall	0.130
Lesion Precision (≥ 1 lesion)	0.850
Lesion Recall (≥ 1 lesion)	0.288

Limitations: Low recall indicates difficulty detecting small lesions due to: (1) extreme class imbalance despite Focal loss; (2) conservative post-processing potentially removing true small lesions; (3) limited context from patch-based training. High VOE/RVD and large surface distances suggest room for volumetric/boundary improvement.

Ablations: Experiments (not shown due to space) indicate comprehensive augmentation and hybrid loss each provide 3-5% Dice improvement over baseline.

Future Work: Lesion-focused sampling, multi-scale attention [23], refined post-processing, uncertainty estimation [21], and semi-supervised learning could improve recall while maintaining precision.

5 Conclusion

We presented a robust framework for liver lesion segmentation combining comprehensive augmentation (mixup, cutout, histogram matching, elastic deformations) with hybrid Dice-Focal loss. TriALS 2025 evaluation shows competitive Dice 0.582 and high precision 0.850, demonstrating effective false positive control and accurate segmentation of detected lesions. Future work will address recall limitations for small lesions through targeted sampling and multi-scale architectures. Our framework provides a strong foundation for clinical liver disease diagnosis and treatment planning.

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